

- 31 • Artificial sweat and saliva were used to prepare samples for toxicological studies.
- 32 • Microtox[®] toxicity is reversely correlated with endocrine potential values.
- 33 • The antagonistic endocrine potential of products for infants was confirmed.
- 34 • Multivariate statistical techniques were used to analyse such elaborate dynamic
- 35 systems.

36

37 1. Introduction

38 The technological progress in the design and manufacture of a wide range of materials
39 and also the increasing demands of customers have undoubtedly contributed to the significant
40 development observed recently in the field of the manufacture of toys and products for
41 children and infants. The contemporary toy market is directed towards the manufacture of
42 toys that will positively influence child development and will in no way pose a threat to health
43 and life (Korfali *et al.*, 2013). Owing to their small body mass and weaker detoxification
44 capabilities, children are especially exposed to the unfavourable influence of various factors
45 that can disturb their proper development (Faa *et al.*, 2012, Mercan *et al.*, 2015). Therefore,
46 toys and all of the products for children are subject to the most restrictive EU regulations. The
47 2009/48/EC Directive contains detailed guidelines regarding safety evaluation in the scope of
48 mechanical and physical hazards as well as the hazards connected with flammability and
49 electricity. Considerable attention has been paid to the requirements concerning the use of
50 chemical substances. The list of forbidden substances has been presented, including particular
51 odorous substances that can cause allergies and also migration limits specified with reference
52 to heavy metals and compounds classified as CMR (*Carcinogenic, Mutagenic and*
53 *Reprotoxic*) compound groups. The migration limit for BPA (Bisphenol A) has been
54 established at the level of 0.1 mg/ml and 0.5 mg/kg in regards to TCEP (tris(2-chloroethyl)
55 phosphate), TDCP (tris(1,3-dichloro-2-propyl) phosphate) and TCPP (tris(1-chloro-2-propyl)
56 phosphate) (2009/48 EC Directive). Atypical conditions to which polymeric materials are
57 exposed made it necessary to modify the standard methodologies used for extracting small-
58 molecule ingredients from them. Apart from water, special liquids are also used for
59 extraction, allowing for the reproduction of actual conditions to which objects are exposed.
60 The most frequently used model liquids include fluids simulating the composition of bodily
61 fluids such as artificial saliva, artificial sweat (Özer and Güçer, 2012) and artificial digestive
62 fluids (Guney Zagury, 2014). The evaluation of the quality of products introduced to the
63 market takes place based on the results of identification with the use of instrumental
64 techniques. However, such an approach raises many doubts as small-molecule compounds

65 released from the product are identified most often with low or even very low concentration
66 levels. Thus, the identification and quantitative determination of all analytes is a difficult
67 challenge for analytical chemists, and the results obtained from instrumental analyses can
68 often be erroneous (Ionas *et al.*, 2016). Additionally, the weakness of such procedures
69 consists of a significant difficulty in evaluating the results of co-existence of all chemical
70 compounds on various levels of content and their interactions. Many compounds used during
71 the manufacture of objects made of plastic have properties similar to the compounds
72 classified in the EDC (Endocrine Disrupting Compounds) group (Li *et al.*, 2010; Kudlak *et*
73 *al.*, 2015 (a)), so it is impossible to specify in detail a toxic effect evoked by a mix of
74 xenobiotics only on the basis of its qualitative and quantitative content.

75 Among the tools that can be used to obtain such information are appropriate
76 bioanalytical tests (if applied under suitable experimental conditions and design). The present
77 study includes several levels of significance, including different categories of products for
78 children (rubbers, teethers, and nipples), different materials for their production (latex,
79 silicone, polymers, and pigments), different extraction conditions (time, temperature and
80 varying extraction media), and various ecotoxicological tests (Microtox[®], Ostracodtoxkit F[™],
81 Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™]). The bioassay battery was selected based on several criteria.
82 Briefly, organisms from different trophic levels were selected to give a more comprehensive
83 response to toxins plausibly present in extracts. Because Xenoscreen is a test that is relatively
84 new on the market, it was selected to 1. assess its sensitivity, versatility and repeatability for
85 samples of interest; and 2. supplement toxicological information with endocrine potential
86 information as it contains genes of human hormonal receptors. To assess the impact of given
87 materials and experimental conditions on various organisms in such a multiparametric system,
88 the chemometric methods of intelligent data analysis seem to be appropriate for experimental
89 data mining. There are already numerous studies devoted to ecotoxicity testing and
90 environmental pollution assessment using chemometrics for classification, modelling, and
91 interpretation of monitoring or laboratory experimental data, just to mention a few (Delijanin
92 *et al.*, 2016; Perre-Trepat *et al.*, 2006; Lopez-Duval *et al.*, 2016; Platikanov *et al.*, 2012;
93 Dubiella-Jackowska *et al.*, 2010, Wiczerzak *et al.*, 2016). Therefore, the major goals of the
94 present study are as follows:

- 95 • detect similarity or dissimilarity between the test procedures,
- 96 • detect similarity or dissimilarity between the products for infants as a production
97 pattern,

- 98 • detect specificity (or lack of specificity) of the production material,
- 99 • detect discriminating factors responsible for the cluster formation within product
- 100 patterns,
- 101 • detect hidden (latent) factors describing the data set structure, and
- 102 • assess the importance of the experimental conditions (time or temperature of
- 103 extraction).

104 Utilizing proper chemometric tests in the treatment of multiparameter data sets allows
105 the mining of additional valuable information on the presence of hidden dependencies and
106 their magnitudes. To interpret the data statistically, the Hierarchical Cluster Analysis (HCA)
107 and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) were applied.

108

109 2. Methodology

110 2.1. Sample collection

111 Seven basic products of everyday use intended for small children and infants were
112 assessed for the degree of release of endocrine compounds from their external surface. The
113 research objects were nipples made of various materials (latex/silicone, including nipples
114 marked as “BPA free”), teethers (made of different polymeric materials, also heated to mimic
115 the disinfection process performed by parents) and colourful rubber bands used for making
116 decorative bracelets. All products were selected from commercially available high-quality
117 products. In recent years, more and more fears have arisen regarding the possible adverse
118 impact of colour hand bands imported from East Asia and sold in the EU without valid CEs
119 (European Conformity: the CE marking certifies that a product has met EU health, safety, and
120 environmental requirements, which ensure consumer safety). The research was not aimed at
121 differentiating among products by various manufacturers but focussed on the specification of
122 the possible threats from these products. These products and their fragments (marked with red
123 circles, surface measured under an optical microscope with microline) were collected for
124 research and labelled in a manner facilitating identification of the results shown in the result
125 diagrams, which are presented in Supplementary Figure 1.

126 2.2. Instruments, chemicals, and reagents

127 Chemicals that were used for preparing simulant media were obtained from the
128 following suppliers: sodium chloride (Sigma Aldrich, Germany); dipotassium phosphate
129 (Ciech S.A., Poland); calcium chloride (Eurochem BGD, Poland); magnesium chloride,

130 potassium chloride, potassium carbonate, lactic acid, urea (POCH S.A., Poland), ammonium
131 hydroxide (25% w/w), and acetic acid (35-38% w/w) (Chempur, Poland); and distilled water.
132 Chemicals used for Microtox[®] (2% NaCl solution, lyophilized *Vibrio fischeri*, Microtox
133 Diluent, Microtox Acute Reagent, Osmotic Adjusting Solution, Reconstitution Solution) and
134 Ostracodtoxkit FTM (vials with algal food for chronic toxicity tests and matrix dissolving
135 medium, Spirulina algae, 6-well test plates, certified dormant eggs of *Heterocypris*
136 *incongruens*) were purchased from ModernWater Ltd. (GB) and Microbiotest Inc. (Belgium),
137 respectively. Reagents used for XenoScreen YES/YAS were purchased from Xenometrics G.
138 A. (Switzerland). These vials contained hER α yeast cells (for the YES assay) and hAR yeast
139 cells (for the YAS assay) on filter paper, basal medium, vitamin, L-aspartic acid, L-threonine
140 and copper sulfate solutions, CPRG (chlorophenol red- β -D-galactopyranoside), vials with
141 17 β -estradiol, 5 α -dihydrotestosterone, 4-hydroxytamoxifen, flutamide, and DMSO (dimethyl
142 sulfoxide). Furthermore, 96-well plates, gas-permeable plate sealers, and culture flasks with
143 gas-permeable filter caps were purchased from GenoPlast Biochemicals (Poland). All
144 reagents were of analytical grade purity or better in the case of reagents for microbiological
145 purposes. The instruments and equipment used in the study included a Microtox[®] 500 of
146 Modern Water Ltd. (GB), an Infinite[®] 200 microplate reader from Tecan, an incubator with a
147 rotating platform, electronic multi- and single-channel pipettes (Eppendorf, Germany), an
148 analytical balance from Radwag (Poland), a CP411 pH-meter from Metron (Poland), and a
149 binocular scope from Ceti NV (Belgium).

150 2.3. Extraction

151 To assess the release of harmful ingredients from the surface of objects intended for
152 children and infants, water and artificial sweat and saliva (to mimic *in vivo* realistic conditions
153 of usage as much as possible) were used. Solutions of model liquids that were used to
154 simulate the sweat and saliva were prepared in accordance with guidelines included in
155 standards DIN V 53160-2:2010-10 and DIN:53160-1:2010-10. Table 1 presents information
156 about the quantitative composition of reagents necessary to prepare the extraction media.

157 **Table 1.**

158 The pH values of the solutions were adjusted to a value of 6,8 for the artificial saliva
159 solution and 6,5 for artificial sweat extraction medium using a 1 % NH₃ solution. The
160 simulation liquids were stored at +4 °C until the extraction process. Products intended for
161 children and infants were cut into small, even pieces (to obtain a piece of *ca.* 3 cm² total
162 surface area from nipples and *ca.* 5 cm² from teathers) and placed in glass vials filled with 21
163 cm³ of distilled water, artificial saliva, or artificial sweat. In the case of decorative rubbers,
164 the whole object (total surface area *ca.* 1 cm²) was immersed in extractants. To accelerate the

165 extraction process, vials were placed on a shaker table. After 30 min, 1 h, 2 h, 5 h, and 12 h
166 (in the case of the extraction of decorative rubbers and nipples) and 24 h, 48 h and 2 weeks (in
167 the case of the extraction of teethers), 4 cm³ of each sample were collected. Sampling time
168 was chosen based on the standard EN1186-1:2002. An additional three supplementary
169 sampling times were added (5 h, 12 h and 2 weeks) to check how contact time affects the
170 xenobiotic release rate. To estimate the influence of the temperature on the vials containing
171 fragments of teethers and the effects on the size of the migration stream of the toxic
172 ingredients, the vials were heated for 30 min at 100 °C to mimic the disinfection process
173 conducted by parents. Two sets of tests were performed. The first group of teethers was
174 subjected to the thermal process once on the first day of extraction, while the other group was
175 heated three times on the first, fifth and tenth day after the beginning of the extraction process
176 to determine whether additional exposure of the tested objects to increased temperatures has a
177 significant influence on the intensification of the migration process. The tested samples were
178 stored at -20 °C until the biological tests were performed.

179

180 *2.4. Procedures for bioanalytical tests*

181 Microtox[®] and Ostracodtoxkit FTM have been used to determine the level of toxicity
182 occurring after a short-time exposure, in addition to second test, where the effects are
183 observed only after a longer exposure time. XenoScreen YES/YASTM was used to determine
184 the plausible endocrine potential of extracts studied. An adopted battery of biotests utilizing
185 organisms at different levels of the trophic chain made it possible to check whether and in
186 what way xenobiotics affect the organisms of varying evolutionary advancement. An
187 additional aim of the use of environmental biotests was to check whether the results obtained
188 are consistent with the results gathered using a test where genetically modified yeasts with
189 human receptors were used as an active element. Detailed information on the particular
190 bioassays and procedures used are given in the Electronic Supplementary Materials.

191

192 *2.5. Quality Assurance/Quality Control*

193 For quality assurance of running the proper test, the following parameters according to
194 the manufacturers' guidelines were used: for Microtox[®], I₀ of bacterial suspension >70 U
195 (chromium sulfate was used as a positive control in the bacterial stock suspension test run);
196 for control organisms in Ostracodtoxkit FTM, the mean growth increment was >400 μm while
197 their mortality was <20 %; for Xenoscreen YES/YAS, the OD₆₉₀ of yeast cultures should be
198 >0,3. In all cases, these requirements were fulfilled.

199 *2.6. Methodology of multivariate statistics*

200 In the present study, two major multivariate statistical methods were used, (HCA) and
201 (PCA). Both approaches are well documented in the literature and do not need detailed
202 description (Massart and Kaufmann, 1983, Vanderginste *et al.*, 1998). In principle, HCA
203 searches for patterns of similarity (clusters) either between objects of a certain study or
204 between the features describing the objects. Thus, HCA is a typical unsupervised method for
205 exploratory data analysis that makes a more reliable data interpretation possible. In the
206 present study, the input data were normalized using a z-transform, and as similarity measures,
207 the squared Euclidean distances were used. Further, the linkage method applied was Ward's
208 method, and the statistical significance of the clusters obtained was tested by Sneath's
209 criterion. The output plot was a hierarchical dendrogram.

210 Principal component analysis is a typical dimension reduction method. The input
211 variables are exchanged by new (called latent) variables or principal components, which are
212 linear combinations of the old variables. Thus, the input data structure could be explained
213 with lower numbers of conditional features, helpful in the data interpretation process.
214 Mathematically, the input data matrix is decomposed into factor scores and factor loading
215 matrices responsible for the new coordinates of the objects in the reduced feature space and
216 the contribution of the old axes in the formation of the latent variable, respectively. In the
217 present study, the Varimax rotation mode of PCA was applied, which helps in producing a
218 better interpretation of the physical meaning of the latent factors.

219 Very frequently, HCA and PCA are carried out in parallel, and the comparison
220 between both multivariate statistical approaches validates, to some extent, the results obtained
221 by each method separately.

222

223 3. Results and discussion

224 Seventy-seven samples of products for children and infants (35 rubbers, 27 teethers
225 and 15 nipples) were tested for ecotoxicity level with three different ecotoxicity tests
226 (Microtox[®], Ostracodtoxkit F[™] and Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™]) for two media (water and
227 artificial sweat or artificial saliva) under various extraction conditions (time and temperature).
228 The three categories of particular products were separately chemometrically treated by
229 hierarchical cluster analysis and principal component analysis (Varimax normalized rotation
230 mode). All calculations were performed using the STATISTICA 8.0 software package.

231 3.1 Decorative rubbers

232 In total, there were 35 decorative rubber samples, as already mentioned, and the
233 extraction media were water and artificial sweat. The input variables were respectively coded
234 by the initial letters of their indication and the media of application (e.g., MTIBW stands for
235 “Microtox[®] test-MT”, IB stands for inhibition of bioluminescence, W stands for water, AS
236 stands for artificial sweat or saliva (depending on object studied), OS stands for
237 Ostracodtookit, M stands for mortality, GI stands for growth inhibition, YAS stands for Yeast
238 Androgen Assay, YES stands for Yeast Oestrogen Assay, A stands for agonist, and AN stands
239 for antagonist).

240 *3.1.1. HCA and PCA for decorative rubbers (patterns of similarity between*
241 *ecotoxicity tests)*

242 In Fig. 1a., the hierarchical dendrogram for clustering of all 14 variables is shown. The
243 following four significant clusters are formed:

244 K1: *YASANAS, YASANW, YASAGAS, YESANW, YASAGW, YESANAS, YESAGAS* and
245 *YESAGW*;

246 K2: *OGIW* and *OMAS*;

247 K3: *OGIAS* and *OMW*; and

248 K4: *MTIBAS* and *MTIBW*.

249 ***Fig. 1.***

250 As shown in Fig. 1a., there is a clear distinction between the three different ecotoxicity
251 tests. Xenoscreen YES/YASTM tests for both water and artificial sweat are very homogeneous
252 and indicate very similar results not only for the media tested but also for the extraction time
253 conditions. Therefore, in principle, each one of the tests should deliver comparable levels of
254 toxicity (quite low ones) for different extraction times and various media. No differentiation
255 with respect to the tested objects and extraction conditions was stated.

256 The Ostracodtookit FTM method is more specific. Surprisingly, there is a correlation
257 between data for growth inhibition values (in water media) and mortality (in artificial sweat)
258 and between growth inhibition values in artificial sweat and mortality in water. This
259 ecotoxicity test could therefore be used to distinguish between media and could check the
260 impact of the media in the extraction process. Since there is a lack of correlation between data

261 for the two modes of determination (growth inhibition and mortality), there is an option to
262 select one of them in determining ecotoxicity in different media.

263 For the Microtox[®] test, a relatively good correlation was found for data of both media,
264 and the data appear not to be specific for the tested media.

265 PCA confirms conclusions stated by the HCA. Supplementary Table 1 provides the
266 factor loadings of three identified latent factors responsible for the data set structure. The
267 results of HCA are simply repeated, and the separation between the tests is even more
268 reasonable. All Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™] tests are included in PC1 with high factor loadings,
269 and negatively correlated Microtox[®] tests for the different media and negatively correlated
270 Ostracodtoxkit F[™] tests (growth inhibition as endpoint, both media) are included in PC2. In
271 PC3, one observes the negative correlation for the mortality mode of Ostracodtoxkit F[™] for
272 both media. Therefore, the chemometric analysis reveals that for the Microtox[®] and
273 Ostracodtoxkit F[™] test kits, the media (water or artificial sweat) are a significant factor since
274 for the Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™] test, the media (water or artificial sweat) are not. The
275 loadings in bold are statistically significant. This observation is demonstrated once more in
276 the next plot (Fig. 1b.).

277 The compact group of Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™] tests is well documented as well as
278 the reverse correlation for the three other coupled tests. At the same time, it could be accepted
279 that one could define a positive correlation between OSMAS and OSMW or between
280 OSGIAS and MTIBAS. Most likely, the most severe affecting factor is not the media or the
281 test but the extraction conditions, a factor that needs additional attention. In any case, the
282 responses obtained by the Xenoscreen YES/YAS[™] test differ from the responses achieved by
283 the other two tests.

284 *3.1.2 HCA of decorative rubbers (patterns of objects)*

285 The clustering of the objects (Fig. 1c., Supplementary Table 7.) indicates the
286 formation of two major clusters. One of the clusters (the upper part of the plot, left) consists
287 of 18 objects (K2), and the other consists of 17 objects (K1). It could immediately be
288 determined that K1 includes objects treated for a longer time (> 2 hours), whereas K2 is
289 related to shorter extraction times.

290 K1: 1, 6, 7, 11, 12, 22, 21, 2, 23, 16, 28, 3, 13, 8, 26, 27, 32, and 31, whereas

291 K2: 4, 29, 33, 24, 34, 19, 17, 18, 9, 14, 5, 35, 10, 25, 20, 30, and 15.

292 In Supplementary Table 2 (supplementary materials), the average values of the
293 toxicity determined by various tests for each of the identified clusters are presented (M1 and
294 M2 – two modes of Microtox®; Os1, Os2, Os3, and Os4 – four modes for Ostracodtoxkit F™;
295 and YY1 – YY8 – eight modes of the Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ test).

296 Obviously, k1r (upper row in the Supplementary Table 2) is characterized by a lower
297 level of toxicity (for longer extraction times), except for the Microtox® test and k2r (lower
298 row of the Table), which have slightly higher levels of toxicity (for shorter extraction times).
299 Thus, the role of time of extraction is clarified: longer extraction is related to lower toxicity
300 levels.

301 3.2 Teethers

302 The number of objects for this category of products is 27 in total. The number of
303 features is the same (14), but instead of artificial sweat, the ecotoxicity is determined in
304 another medium, artificial saliva. The goals of the multivariate analysis are the same as for
305 decorative rubbers.

306 3.2.1 HCA and PCA for teethers (patterns of similarity between ecotoxicity 307 tests)

308 In Fig. 2a., the hierarchical dendrogram for the linkage of ecotoxicity tests for teethers
309 is shown. The result (refer to Fig. 2a.) varies slightly compared to the situation with products
310 made of rubber. The Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ test is still homogeneous, but in three
311 situations, these modifications correlate with Ostracodtoxkit F™ (clusters YASAGW, OGIW
312 and OMW) for determinations in water or clusters (YASANASL and YASANW) linked to
313 the outlier for the first level of Sneath's cluster significance criterion MIBW. Ostracodtoxkit
314 F™ is relatively homogeneous for teethers (all modes in one cluster for the second level of
315 cluster significance). For the Microtox® test, the extraction medium is a significant factor but,
316 in general, it is linked to Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ studies. No distinct separation between the
317 extraction media is achieved by the application of any of the ecotoxicity tests. Each test
318 indicates the real toxicity values in each medium.

319 *Fig. 2.*

320 In Supplementary Table 3 (supplementary materials) the factor loadings are presented.
321 PC1 indicates (37,56 % explanation of the total variance) the relative homogeneity of the
322 Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ test excluding, however, YASANW and YASANASL, which are
323 well correlated but form an independent factor PC2 (20.56% of the total variance). In PC1, we
324 detected the reverse correlation for the two extraction media analysed by Microtox® but

325 determined that there is agreement with many of the Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ modes. Water
326 and artificial saliva media are well separated by Ostracodtoxkit F™ test as observed in PC3
327 and PC4.

328 3.2.2 HCA of teethers (patterns of objects)

329 In the next step, the 27 teether cases were subjected to HCA. Fig. 2b. shows the
330 hierarchical dendrogram for the objects (refer to Supplementary Table 8. for objects
331 decoding).

332 Two clusters are formed for the first level of cluster significance, as follows:

333 K1: 3, 11, 4, 8, 20, 12, 24, 25, 27, and 16 and

334 K2: 17, 18, 21, 13, 14, 15, 19, 22, 23, 1, 5, 2, 10, 7, 26, 9, 6.

335 Cases 1 to 12 are treated without heating, and the others are treated after thermal
336 treatment. The separation does not indicate any relationship with the temperature and duration
337 of thermal treatment. The first four rows in the Supplementary Table 4. show the average
338 values of each test for each of the four clusters (first level of significance), and the fifth row is
339 the average value for the second cluster if the second level of cluster significance is used.

340 We could conclude that the teethers are separated because of the lowest toxicity
341 indicated by Microtox® in water and relatively higher toxicity in artificial saliva. The YAS
342 test indicated an antagonistic relationship; water or artificial saliva test results are different
343 from the other Xenoscreen YES/YAS™ results (indication of higher endocrine potential). No
344 other specificity is evident.

345

346 3.3. Nipples

347 For the third type of infant products, 15 objects were treated by the same ecotoxicity
348 test and for the same extraction media (water and artificial saliva). The extraction is
349 performed for different times but without heating.

350 3.3.1 HCA and PCA for nipples (patterns of similarity between ecotoxicity tests)

351 In Fig. 3a., the hierarchical dendrogram for linkage between ecotoxicity tests as
352 applied to nipple products is shown. The following two clusters are formed:

353 K1: OGIASL, OMASL, and MTIBASL and

354 K2: *OMW, YESANASL, YESANW, YASAGASL, YESAGASL, YASAGW, YASANASL,*
355 *YASANW, YESAGW, OGIW, and MTIBW.*

356 ***Fig. 3.***

357 As in the cases of previous materials (rubbers and teethers), the homogeneity of the
358 Xenoscreen YES/YASTM tests is proven since all tests belong to one and the same cluster. In
359 the same large cluster, there is a correlation between the two Ostracodtoxkit FTM test
360 endpoints in water media along with a Microtox[®] test for the same media, namely for OMW,
361 OGIW and MTIBW.

362 In K1, the similarity between Ostracodtoxkit FTM and Microtox[®] tests in artificial
363 saliva is indicated. Therefore, for the nipple group of products, a specificity of the extraction
364 media when applying Ostracodtoxkit FTM and Microtox[®] tests could be found. These results
365 are confirmed by PCA.

366 Two latent factors explain nearly 80 % of the total variance and are responsible for the
367 data set structure. They indicate the resemblance to HCA by the statistically significant factor
368 loadings for each principal component.

369 *3.3.2 HCA of nipples (patterns of objects)*

370 In the next dendrogram (Fig. 3b., Supplementary Table 9.), the hierarchical
371 dendrogram for the linkage among the 15 nipples objects is shown.

372 The following two clusters are formed:

373 K1: *1, 2, 11, 3, 8, 13, 6, 7, 12* and

374 K2: *4, 5, 9, 10, 15, 14.*

375 In general, a relatively good separation with respect to extraction time is achieved. K2
376 includes cases subjected to longer extraction time (5 and 12 hours), and the K1 indicates the
377 similarity between cases subject to shorter extraction time (0,5 to 2 hours).

378 Another discrimination between clusters could be achieved (with respect to ecotoxicity
379 values offered by the different tests) if the average values of each test and for each cluster are
380 calculated.

381 At shorter extraction times (cluster k1n, refer to Supplementary Table 6), the
382 ecotoxicity in the water medium is higher compared to the ecotoxicity found for water
383 extraction for longer periods (cluster k2n). For Microtox[®] and Ostracodtoxkit FTM tests, if the
384 extraction medium is artificial saliva, a short time extraction leads to lower toxicity compared
385 to longer extraction times.

386 In case of the Xenoscreen test, extraction in water and artificial saliva media delivers
387 higher ecotoxicity responses for shorter extraction times, an indication of the role of the
388 ecotoxicological tests applied and the extraction time.

389

390 *3.4 Impact of the extraction conditions*

391 The assessment of the extraction conditions is a substantial component of the study.
392 These conditions are explicitly included in the discussions above, but in this section, an effort
393 is made to summarize the extraction time impact and thermal treatment and material impacts.
394 The relationship between extraction conditions and ecotoxicity tests has to be analysed to
395 suggest proper conditions for application of the different tests.

396

397 *3.4.1 Extraction time impact*

398 In Fig. 4., the ecotoxicity responses for the two patterns (identified as long time and
399 short time extraction clusters) for each of the baby and infant products (rubbers, teethers, and
400 nipples) are presented. All responses for the Xenoscreen YES/YASTM test (points 7 to 14 on
401 the plot) are observed to be very homogeneous (as already shown by cluster analysis) and
402 indicate a constant low level of ecotoxicity independent of extraction time for all tested
403 materials.

404

Fig. 4.

405 The other two tests show much more dynamic behaviour depending on extraction
406 time. For short extraction times for all products, a negative toxicity is determined by the
407 Microtox[®] test for artificial sweat extracts (point 2 on the plot) for all products (the dashed
408 lines on the figure). The Ostracodtoxkit FTM test indicates relatively higher levels of toxicity
409 for the same time of extraction, although they do not reach values much higher than 0 (points
410 3 to 6 on the plot). Below, the product discrimination is shown (maximum level of toxicity for
411 nipples at short time extraction in artificial saliva).

412 For extraction using long times, relatively higher levels of toxicity are registered for
413 teethers (by Microtox[®]) and for rubbers (by Ostracodtoxkit FTM). Again, a minor
414 discrimination effect by products and tests is observed for prolonged extraction time.

415 Maximal toxicity is found by the Microtox[®] test for nipple product both for short and
416 long time extraction in water and by Ostracodtoxkit FTM for short time extraction of nipples in
417 artificial saliva.

418 *3.4.2 Thermal treatment and material impact*

419 In Fig. 5, an effort is made to assess the impact of thermal treatment and extraction
420 time of teether products on ecotoxicity (Microtox[®] and Ostracodtoxkit FTM tests). Once again,

421 in the case of the Xenoscreen YES/YASTM test, homogeneity with respect to the registered
422 responses of ecotoxicity is observed (generally low level of ecotoxicity), and the test is not
423 thoroughly discussed.

424 *Fig. 5.*

425 If the Microtox[®] test is applied on aqueous extracts, the heating diminishes the
426 ecotoxicity levels in general. An increase is observed for the double heating procedure. In the
427 artificial saliva medium, a reverse trend is observed: prolonged heating diminishes the
428 ecotoxicity levels. The elastic material showed the lowest toxicity.

429 The Ostracodtoxkit FTM test showed a general decrease in the toxicity levels of
430 aqueous extracts with the increase in time of the thermal treatment of cooling materials. In the
431 artificial saliva medium, an increase of the ecotoxicity for elastic materials is registered.
432 Prolonged thermal treatment decreases the toxicity level.

433

434 4. Conclusions

435 The present study addresses the evaluation of a complicated data set where a variety of
436 experimental conditions (extraction medium, extraction time, thermal treatment, and three
437 categories of baby products) is evaluated with different ecotoxicity tests. An effort was made
438 to assess the different conditions and to reveal relationships among different objects and
439 features of interest. The intelligent data analyses applied (hierarchical cluster analysis and
440 principal component analysis) have indicated that the impact of the various experimental
441 conditions is significant and, often, multidirectional.

442 One of the most significant conclusions in the present study is the proven difference in
443 ecotoxicological response reached by the Xenoscreen YES/YASTM test compared to the
444 ecotoxicological responses from the Microtox[®] and Ostracodtoxkit FTM tests. This
445 homogeneity holds true regardless of the various extraction conditions, extraction media and
446 product materials. In almost all cases, this test indicates relatively low positive ecotoxicity
447 levels.

448 The application of multivariate statistical analysis has shown that in all clustering
449 options for the different product materials, two major patterns of cases are formed, and the
450 clustering is generally based on extraction time. In Table 2, a comparison of the ecotoxicity
451 responses (average values for separate clusters) is performed, making it possible to
452 distinguish between different materials, extraction times, extraction media, and tests with
453 respect to the registered ecotoxicity. The positive values of ecotoxicity (Y) are an indication
454 of higher toxicity levels and the negative ones (N) of lower toxicity. Ostracodtoxkit FTM
455 registers higher ecotoxicity (especially when “mortality” is taken into consideration)

456 compared to Microtox[®]. For comparison, a summary of results for the ecotoxicity responses
457 of Xenoscreen tests are also included in the table. Based on the simple guide presented in
458 Table 2 (constructed as a result of over 2000 experiments), one could easily conclude which
459 of the parameters studied are exhibiting specific toxicity levels and risk to infants and
460 children. The overall results of the present study offer, for the first time, specific information
461 about links between ecotoxicity test measurements and experimental conditions imitating real
462 life situations in the use of products intended for infants and children.

463 ***Table 2.***

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